

USING INDICATORS TO DETERMINE THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article deals with one of the modern methods for assessing the quality of education, the use of a set of indicators (indicators) in the educational process.*

Keywords: *multimedia, integral, indicator, monitoring, object.*

INTRODUCTION

An objective assessment of the level of knowledge of students allows organizing and conducting classes at a higher quality level and, if necessary, introducing corrections in working curricula, while the flexibility of organizing the educational process can only be achieved if the following conditions are met: with clearly defined learning goals; strict observance of proportions between sections of the material being read in time; active involvement of students in the process of mastering new material; skillful and competent use of interactive methods using multimedia technologies; continuous monitoring of the assimilation of new material by trainees through oral express surveys with the obligatory announcement of the assessment; use of indicators to determine the level of knowledge of students.

MAIN PART

In our opinion, one of the modern methods for assessing the quality of education is monitoring the quality of education, which will allow not only to determine the level of mastering the discipline, but the strengths and weaknesses of the methodology of teaching the discipline by a particular teacher, the use of innovative technologies of pedagogy. The proposed procedure for using a set of indicators is aimed at establishing the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of an object [1].

The following concepts are used in the article: the quality of education is an integral characteristic of the education system, reflecting the degree of compliance of the actual achieved educational results with regulatory requirements, social and personal expectations. Quality assessment is a process that determines the degree of compliance of the measured educational results, the conditions for their provision with the standard as a generally recognized system of requirements for the quality of education fixed in regulatory documents. Monitoring the quality of education is a system for collecting, processing data on indicators, storing and providing information on the quality of education in the course of assessing the educational activities of students. The set of indicators ensures the coordination of monitoring systems for assessing the quality of education, they characterize the main elements of the quality of education (the quality of goals, the quality of conditions, the quality of the process, the quality of the result) and meet the following requirements: consistency with the generally accepted system for assessing the quality of education; the expediency of their use for making managerial decisions, in procedures for determining the level of knowledge; possibility of quantitative measurement; unambiguous interpretation of indicator values. In our case, monitoring is a procedure for evaluating students as part of an intermediate and final control. With the appropriate development of a set of indicators

that characterize the main components of the quality of education (goals, conditions, quality of the process, quality of the result), they can be used in the system for assessing the quality of education.

The indicators have been developed for the following purposes:

- 1) educational and extracurricular achievements of students;
- 2) curricula that determine the content of education at various levels and directions;
- 3) organization of the educational process;
- 4) availability of resources;
- 5) use of ICT technologies.

Monitoring can be carried out in two forms: continuous monitoring (carried out continuously by a system of requests and reporting indicators) and periodic monitoring (carried out periodically) in accordance with the plan of monitoring studies. Monitoring involves the widespread use of modern information technologies at all stages of collecting, processing, storing and using information. Storage and operational use of information is carried out through electronic communication and regularly updated electronic databases.

The implementation of monitoring involves the sequence of the following actions:

- 1) definition and justification of the object of monitoring;
- 2) collection of data used for monitoring;
- 3) structuring databases that provide storage and operational use of information;
- 4) processing of received data in the course of monitoring;
- 5) analysis and interpretation of the data obtained in the course of monitoring;
- 6) preparation of documents based on the results of the analysis of the received data;
- 7) dissemination of monitoring results among monitoring users;
- 8) submission of research results to the database of the educational institution.

The main users of information on the results of the assessment of the quality of education are:

- 1) students and their parents (legal representatives);
- 2) teaching staff;
- 3) teaching staff of the educational institution;
- 3) bodies that manage education;
- 4) employers;
- 5) the public.

The results of evaluation procedures can be the basis for making informed decisions at different levels of management of an educational institution. The structure of the complex of indicators includes a complex of indicators having a matrix structure that involves evaluation by objects and by levels.

2. Indicators have been developed for the following assessment objects:

- 1) educational and extracurricular achievements of students,
- 2) educational programs that determine the content of education at various levels and directions;
- 3) departments and deans (organization of the educational process);
- 4) educational systems (provision of resources).

The set of indicators is the following hierarchical structure and includes:

- 1) the individual level of the student;
- 2) the level of the teaching staff;

3) the level of the department;

4) faculty level;

The proposed set of indicators will allow you to optimally organize the educational process in terms of the quality of education. With the skillful organization of such a scenario for conducting a training session, it is possible to achieve an increase in motivation, trainees and, as a result, an increase in the quality of training. Obviously, for the organization of such classes, material support plays an important role, meaning the availability of handouts, multimedia equipment and other technical training aids. To assess the quality of education, it is proposed to use training tests during a frontal survey of students in a computer class. Experimental training sessions held at TUIT in the study of special disciplines revealed both positive and negative aspects of these pedagogical technologies. The purpose of the experiment was to study the effectiveness of the use of interactive methods using multimedia tools, on the one hand, and the use of training tests, on the other hand.

CONCLUSION

Of particular interest are training tests, where, along with the traditional method of determining the level of knowledge of students, they were offered the correct answer with an indication of the source up to the section, paragraph and page where the correct answer is stated. For simplicity, one main source was taken as a source; in the future, for a deeper study of the material and for independent work, several sources will be taken. We hope that such an innovative approach will increase the motivation of students to study special disciplines, which will undoubtedly have a positive impact on the level of graduate professional education.

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